

The Condensation of Ketones with Resorcinol.

Part I. Condensation by Addition.

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The condensations of ketones with aromatic hydroxy-compounds appear not to have been systematically studied, though a few scattered instances may be found in the chemical literature. The object of the present work was to investigate the condensation of one molecule of a ketone with (a) one molecule of the hydroxy-compound (by addition), and (b) with two molecules of the hydroxy-compound by the elimination of water. In Part II of this paper the condensation of the second type will be described, those of the first type being dealt with in the present paper.

For the condensation of type (a) dilute hydrochloric acid (1:1) has been found to be the best condensing agent, the reaction usually taking place at the temperature of the boiling water-bath. In the condensation of acetone with resorcinol, it is interesting to observe that acetone is first converted into mesityl oxide, which subsequently condenses with one molecule of resorcinol giving a colourless product (I), the mechanism of the reaction being thus represented.

This view is confirmed by the observation that mesityl oxide, when condensed with resorcinol under similar conditions gives a product identical with (I). The product (I) gives a coloured monopotassium salt having presumably a quinonoid configuration (II),

a faintly coloured monobenzoyl derivative (quinonoid) and a colourless diacetyl derivative (non-quinonoid) $(\text{AcO})_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3 \cdot \text{C}(\text{OH})(\text{CH}_3) \cdot \text{CH} : \text{CMe}_2$. The ethylene linkage in the product is

established by the fact that when its alcoholic solution is treated with bromine, a dibromo-addition product is precipitated, which dissolves on further addition of bromine and gives a tribromo-derivative.

Pyrogallol also condenses with acetone under similar conditions, the product $(\text{OH})_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_2 \cdot \text{C}(\text{OH})(\text{CH}_3) \cdot \text{CH} : \text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ (III) being obtained.

Methyl ethyl ketone and acetophenone under similar conditions are also first transformed into the intermediate products of the mesityl oxide type (not-separated) which then condense with one molecule of resorcinol giving respectively the products

which, as in the case of product (I), give coloured monopotassium salts, monobenzoyl derivatives and almost colourless diacetyl derivatives.

When cyclohexanone and resorcinol were condensed in aqueous solution, two compounds were isolated, one insoluble in alkali which is presumably a polymerisation product of the ketone and the other an alkali soluble product (VI) having the formula $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_3$ resulting from the condensation of resorcinol and the intermediate ketone. The yield of the condensation product with resorcinol is much better in alcoholic solution than in aqueous solution. The product behaves towards alkali like (I), and gives a monobenzoyl derivative, a diacetyl derivative and a dibromo-derivative.

From a study of the above compounds it appears that in the case of the simple ketones intermediate compounds of the mesityl oxide type are first formed which then react with resorcinol; no

condensation with resorcinol taking place in the absence of the formation of such intermediate ketones as in the case of camphor and benzophenone. It is also observed that mesityl oxide reacts with resorcinol readily giving almost theoretical yield whilst acetone reacts after a long time. It is therefore inferred that the grouping $-\text{CO}-\text{C}=\text{C}-$ in a ketone is essential for this type of condensation, and this view is further confirmed by the fact that such ketones as isatin, benzalacetophenone and benzoylacetone, all readily condense with resorcinol giving almost theoretical yields of the products (VII), (VIII) and (IX) respectively. The condensation products with isatin (VII) and with benzalacetophenone (VIII) give deeply coloured potassium salts (X) and (XI), coloured benzoyl derivatives and almost colourless acetyl derivatives.

This type of condensation by addition does not take place between resorcinol and benzophenone or trihydroxybenzophenone in presence of dilute hydrochloric acid; if, however, the acidic character of the phenyl group is diminished as in Michler's ketone, condensation with resorcinol takes place in molecular proportion by addition, yielding dihydroxymalachite green (XII) which dissolves in

concentrated hydrochloric acid with a pink colour changing to bluish-green on dilution; the hydrochloride (XIII) dyes wool a blue shade.

It is interesting to note that the introduction of two OH-groups in *ortho*- and *para*-positions to the methane carbon atom in malachite green, changes the shade from green to blue.

From a study of the dyeing properties of the compounds described in this paper it is found that where the compound is a derivative of triphenylmethane, the tinctorial character is most marked; in the case of the diphenylmethane derivatives the dyeing property is weakened and it practically disappears when the compound contains only one phenyl nucleus in the molecule as in the condensation products of aliphatic and alicyclic ketones with resorcinol.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The condensations of the ketones with resorcinol were carried out by the following *general method*.

The ketone and resorcinol in molecular proportion were mixed in aqueous or alcoholic solution and the mixture was heated with dilute hydrochloric acid (1 vol. of conc. acid and 1 vol. of water)

on the water-bath for several hours. A solid mass gradually separated, which was filtered and extracted with dilute caustic soda solution. The filtered alkaline solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid. The process was repeated two or three times when the product separated as a micro-crystalline solid. It was filtered, thoroughly washed and recrystallised. The condensation products were invariably soluble in alcohol, benzene, acetone, etc. but insoluble in water.

2:4-Dihydroxyphenylmethylisobutenylcarbinol (I).—When a solution of resorcinol (5.5 g.) and acetone (8 c.c.) in 50 c.c. of water was heated with 15 c.c. of dilute hydrochloric acid for 14 hours, as stated above, the product was obtained in 80% yield, which separates from dilute alcohol as a micro-crystalline solid melting at 153°. (Found: C, 69.2; H, 7.9. $C_{12}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 69.2; H, 7.7 per cent.).

It is an almost colourless solid, dissolves in dilute caustic soda solution with a deep orange colour, and gives a yellowish-green colour in concentrated sulphuric acid solution. It is soluble in alcohol, benzene, ether and chloroform but insoluble in water.

Potassium Salt (II).—The substance was dissolved in a dilute alcoholic solution of pure caustic potash so that an excess of it was present. The excess was filtered off and the coloured solution carefully evaporated to dryness, extracted with small quantities of alcohol and filtered off. The potassium salt is a deeply coloured solid. (Found: K, 17.1. $C_{12}H_{13}O_2K$ requires K, 17.1 per cent.).

Benzoyl Derivative.—The benzoyl compound was obtained as a slightly coloured solid by Schotten-Baumann's method; crystallised from alcohol, it melts at 145°. (Found: C, 77.2; H, 6.3. $C_{19}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 77.6; H, 6.1 per cent.).

Acetyl Derivative.—1.5 G. of the substance were refluxed with 25 c. c. of acetic anhydride and a little zinc dust (1 g.) for two hours. The solution was then poured into 200 c. c. of water and 20 c. c. of alcohol and heated. When the anhydride had completely decomposed the whole was cooled and the precipitate was filtered off, washed with dilute alkali and water and crystallised from alcohol; it was obtained as a colourless solid melting at 162°. (Found: C, 65.5; H, 7.2. $C_{16}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 65.81; H, 6.95 per cent.).

Dibromo-derivative.—To an alcoholic solution of the carbinol, the required quantity of bromine was added; the precipitate collected, washed, dissolved in alcohol and reprecipitated by water. Crystallised

by slow evaporation of alcoholic solution it melts at 146°-147°. (Found: Br, 48.1. $C_{12}H_{16}O_3Br_2$ requires Br, 48.5 per cent.)

Tribromo-derivative.—A slight excess of bromine was added to the alcoholic solution of the carbinol. The precipitate of the dibromo-derivative gradually dissolved. After some time the alcoholic solution was poured into water and the solid precipitate collected, washed and crystallised from dilute alcohol; it melts at 136°. (Found: Br, 58.8. $C_{12}H_{15}O_3Br_3$ requires Br, 58.7 per cent.)

Condensation of Mesityl Oxide with Resorcinol (I).—When a mixture of resorcinol (1.5 g.), water (25 c. c.), mesityl oxide (0.98 g.) and dilute hydrochloric acid (5.7 c. c.) was heated under reflux on a water-bath for 4 hours, the condensation product was obtained after the usual treatment, in almost theoretical yield. It crystallised from dilute alcohol; m.p. 152°-153°. (Found: C, 69.2; H, 7.5 per cent.)

It is found to be identical with the product obtained from resorcinol and acetone, already described.

2:4-Dihydroxyphenylethylisopentanylcarbinol (IV).—Resorcinol (8.3 g.), water (45 c. c.), methyl ethyl ketone (6 c. c.) and dilute hydrochloric acid (12 c. c.) on heating for 14 hours gave after usual treatment an almost colourless solid in 80 per cent. yield. It separates from dilute alcohol and melts at 118°. (Found: C, 71.7; H, 8.2. $C_{14}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 71.8; H, 8.5 per cent.)

It dissolves in alkali with a pink colour and in concentrated sulphuric acid solution gives a yellow shade. In solubility it resembles the compound (I).

Benzoyl Derivative.—Prepared in the usual manner, it crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and benzene as a slightly coloured micro-crystalline solid, m. p. 126°. (Found: C, 78.1; H, 6.75. $C_{21}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 78.3; H, 6.8 per cent.)

Acetyl Derivative.—Prepared as in the case of compound (I), it was obtained as a colourless solid from dilute alcohol, m. p. 108°. (Found: C, 67.8; H, 7.5. $C_{18}H_{34}O_5$ requires C, 67.5; H, 7.5 per cent.)

2:4:6-Trihydroxyphenylmethylisobutanylcarbinol (III).—Pyrogallol (6 g.) in 50 c. c. of water was condensed with acetone (8 c. c.) in presence of dilute hydrochloric acid (15 c. c.) by heating for 15 hours; the product was obtained in about 75-80 per cent. yield. On slow evaporation of an alcoholic solution it is obtained as a slightly coloured solid, which does not melt but decomposes at a high temperature.

(Found: C, 64.0; H, 7.2. $C_{12}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 64.3; H, 7.1 per cent.).

In alkaline solution it gives a dark brown colour and it dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a deep orange shade.

2:4-Dihydroxyphenyl-β-methylstyrylphenylcarbinol (V).—Acetophenone (6.5 g.) on being condensed with resorcinol (5.5 g.) in alcohol (30 c. c.) and dilute hydrochloric acid (15 c. c.) by heating for 19 hours gave from the alkaline extract of the product after the removal of unchanged acetophenone by benzene about 40 per cent. yield. On being crystallised by slow evaporation of an alcoholic solution it was obtained as a dark brown powder melting at 132°–134°. (Found: C, 79.6; H, 6.3. $C_{22}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 79.6; H, 6.0 per cent.).

It dissolves in alkali with a dark brown colour and in concentrated sulphuric acid with deep orange shade; it is soluble in alcohol, benzene, etc. but insoluble in water.

Potassium Salt.—Prepared in the usual way, it dissolves in water and even in alcohol and is deeply coloured in the solid state. (Found: K, 11.0. $C_{22}H_{17}O_2K$ requires K, 11.0 per cent.).

Benzoyl Derivative.—The free compound on being benzoylated in alkaline solution gave a somewhat coloured solid which crystallised from a mixture of acetone and alcohol melting at 141°. (Found: C, 83.1; H, 5.3. $C_{29}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 83.3; H, 5.3 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative is obtained in a manner already described. It crystallised from dilute alcohol and melted at 133°. (Found: C, 75.4; H, 6.3. $C_{26}H_{24}O_5$ requires C, 75.2; H, 6.2 per cent.).

2-cycloHexylidene-2: 4-dihydroxyphenyl-cyclohexane-(1)-ol (VI).—On condensing resorcinol (5.5 g.) cyclohexanone (8.5 c. c.) in alcoholic solution with 15 c. c. of dilute hydrochloric acid by heating for 20 hours, the alkali soluble condensation product was obtained in about 80 per cent. yield, which crystallised from dilute alcohol and melts at about 140°. (Found: C, 74.9; H, 8.4. $C_{16}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 75.0; H, 8.3 per cent.).

It decolourises bromine very easily, gives a brown colour in concentrated sulphuric acid solution and dark brown in alkaline solution. It is slightly yellow in colour in the free state.

The *benzoyl* derivative crystallises from a mixture of benzene and alcohol; m. p. 150°. (Found: C, 80.1; H, 6.9. $C_{25}H_{26}O_5$ requires C, 80.2; H, 6.9 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallises from alcohol and benzene;

m. p. 155°. (Found: C, 70.2; H, 7.9. $C_{22}H_{23}O_5$ requires C, 70.2; H, 7.7 per cent.).

Condensation of Isatin and Resorcinol (VII).—On heating a solution of isatin (4.4 g.), resorcinol (3.5 g.) in 150 c.c. of water with 15 c.c. of dilute hydrochloric acid for 5 hours, the product was obtained in almost theoretical yield. It separates from dilute alcohol; it does not melt but decomposes at a high temperature. (Found: C, 65.2; H, 4.2; N, 5.3. $C_{14}H_{11}O_4N$ requires C, 65.4; H, 4.3; N, 5.5 per cent.).

Its solution in alkali is of deep pink colour while in concentrated sulphuric acid it shows an orange-yellow tinge.

The *dipotassium* salt was prepared in the usual way and purified by precipitation with alcohol from concentrated aqueous solution. (Found: K, 24.5. $C_{14}H_7O_3NK_2$ requires K, 24.8 per cent.).

The *dibenzoyl* derivative crystallises from a mixture of acetone and alcohol as a somewhat coloured solid which decomposes at a high temperature. (Found: C, 75.0; H, 4.1. $C_{28}H_{17}O_5N$ requires C, 75.2; H, 3.8 per cent.).

Triacetyl Derivative.—Prepared in the usual way, it crystallises from a mixture of benzene and alcohol and decomposes at a high temperature. (Found: C, 62.6; H, 4.4. $C_{20}H_{17}O_7N$ requires C, 62.6; H, 4.4 per cent.).

2:4-Dihydroxyphenyl phenylstyrylcarbinol (VIII).—Benzylidene acetophenone (6.1 g.), resorcinol (3.35 g.) on heating for 12–14 hours and separating slight excess of the ketone, gave about theoretical yield of the condensation product which crystallises from dilute alcohol; m. p. about 190°. (Found: C, 79.7; H, 5.6. $C_{21}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 79.2; H, 5.7 per cent.).

The *potassium* salt is a deeply coloured solid soluble in alcohol. (Found: K, 11.8. $C_{21}H_{15}O_2K$ requires K, 11.5 per cent.).

Benzoyl Derivative.—Prepared in the usual way, it crystallises from alcohol-benzene; m. p. 128–130°. (Found: C, 83.8; H, 5.2. $C_{28}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 83.2; H, 5.0 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative is prepared as usual: crystallised from alcohol-benzene; m. p. 153°. (Found: C, 74.3; H, 5.6. $C_{25}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 74.6; H, 5.5 per cent.).

2:4-Dihydroxyphenyl phenylacetylcarbinol (IX).—When a solution of resorcinol (2.25 g.), benzoylacetone (3 g.) in alcohol was heated with 12 c.c. of dilute hydrochloric acid, a yield of about 80% of the product was obtained after the usual treatment. It crystallises

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from dilute alcohol, and does not melt but decomposes at a high temperature. (Found: C, 70·5; H, 5·6. $C_{16}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 70·6; H, 5·9 per cent.).

2:4-Dihydroxyphenyltetramethyldiaminodiphenylcarbinol or *Dihydrozomalachite Green* (XIV).—Michler's ketone (5 g.) was heated with resoreinol (2·25 g.) in 50 c.c. of dilute hydrochloric acid for 15 hours. The condensation product was obtained in about 20% yield, which is soluble in excess of acid and alkali. After neutralisation of the acid solution with dilute alkali, the product is purified by washing with ether and hot benzene; it melts at about 168°, (Found: N, 7·4. $C_{23}H_{24}O_2N_2$ requires N, 7·8 per cent.).

It is a deep blue powder. In concentrated hydrochloric acid solution it gives a pink shade which changes to bluish-green on dilution. Its solution in concentrated sulphuric acid is orange-red in colour. It is soluble in alcohol and acetone but insoluble in ether, chloroform and benzene.

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